

Results of the survey of the ZKI working group Strategy and Organization on software solutions at universities 2022

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Introduction

In 2021, the ZKI Strategy and Organization Working Group conducted an initial survey on software solutions at universities¹. Due to strong demand and a lot of feedback on the usefulness of the results, the survey was repeated in 2022 in an expanded form. The survey collects which concrete software solutions for the respective application areas (categories) are used at the universities and how satisfied the users are with the solution, which operating models were selected, which license models the software solutions have and whether a replacement by another software is planned. The naming of several parallel solutions for a category was facilitated and additionally extended by the specification, by which solutions if necessary is to be replaced. In addition, there were responses from institutions in Austria, Switzerland and Germany in 2022. From Germany, universities from all federal states participated. The survey was open over the summer from June 20, 2022 to August 21, 2022 and received information from 142 institutions on nearly 2400 software solutions in use. Due to the broader data base, it was possible to create a significantly expanded evaluation this year.

The following software categories were queried:

- Backup Software
- Campus Management
- Chat / Instant Messaging
- CMS - Content Management System
- DMS - Document Management System
- FIS - Research Information System
- ITSM - IT Service Management
- Calendar
- LMS - Learning Management System
- Mail
- Project Management
- RM - Resource Management
- Sync-n-Share
- Ticket / Incident Management
- Event Management
- Video conferencing
- Video Management
- Virtualization / IaaS
- Knowledge Management

Uniform questions were asked for each category:

- Which solution do you use?

¹ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4817794>

- Is the system commercial, open source, homegrown or hybrid ?²
- How do you operate the system? Internally, externally or mixed?
- How satisfied are you with the solution? (Scale from 1 - very dissatisfied to 10 - very satisfied)
- Should the software be replaced and if so, by what?
- What comments do you have?

In addition, the type of university, country, state, and number of students at the institution could be specified.

The results of those categories that were already collected in the 2021 survey could be collected and evaluated in more detail this year as selectable responses. New solutions were only recorded as free-text responses. The new categories "ITSM" and "Event Management" could also only be answered with free text. This means that a more in-depth analysis of these solutions will not be possible until the next survey.

² <https://de.wikipedia.org/wiki/Mehrfachlizenzierung>

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Sync and Share	82
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Summary

The individual categories differ very clearly in the spectrum of software used. Some categories are dominated by individual solutions, which are used in more than 60% of installations. Examples include Typo3, Nextcloud, Codia d.3, Microsoft Exchange and VMWare. In contrast, categories such as chat or video conferencing solutions are characterized by several solutions with larger shares.

For operation, almost 50% of the software solutions rely on hosting and operation on site, supplemented by 11% with hosting on site and operation from an external source. Around a quarter of the solutions are hosted and operated externally.

In terms of licensing models, commercial licenses are in first place overall with 53%. The open source licenses come in at 31%. However, if hybrid licenses are also included in the range of open source licenses, these types of licenses are at 43%. A more differentiated picture emerges for individual categories. For example, open source and hybrid licenses clearly predominate in the categories LMS, project management software, video management, sync and share, and ticket / incident management.

When comparing the types of HEIs, there are a few categories where the solutions used differ greatly among the types of HEIs, such as the use of Microsoft Teams for the chat category, which is used by over 50% of the participating HEIs for applied sciences, but only by around 25% of the universities. In most cases, however, differences in the use of certain software solutions become apparent when looking at the size of the institution. For example, Zammad or VIMP tend to be used only by institutions with up to 5,000 students, while Seafile or Clarivate Converis are used predominantly by larger institutions with over 15,000 students.

It is also noticeable that many institutions operate several software solutions for most categories, and not only when a change of solution is imminent. Clear examples of this are the backup and video conferencing categories.

The further evaluation is divided into three areas:

- Details of the participating facilities
- Comprehensive evaluations of the solutions as well as operating and licensing models
- Individual evaluations for the categories

Top 5 solutions

The following chart shows the top solutions for each category. Open source solutions are highlighted in green, hybrid licenses in light green, and commercial solutions in blue.

Category	Place 1	Place 2	Place 3	Place 4	Place 5
Backup	Veeam	IBM Spectrum Protect	Bacula	CommVault	Dell EMC Networker
Campus Management	HISinOne	HIS GX	CampusNet	SAP SLCM	CAMPUSonline
Chat / Instant Messaging	Microsoft Teams	RocketChat	Matrix	Cisco Webex	Mattermost
CMS - Content Management	Typo3	Wordpress	Drupal	Plone	FirstSpirit
DMS - Document Management System	Codia d.3	Alfresco	DocuWare	Lib-IT Filero	ELO Digital Office
Research Information System	HISinOne-RES	In-house development	Clarivate Converis	Elsevier Pure	DSPACE-CRIS
IT Service Management	i-doit	JIRA Service Management	KIX	TOPdesk	Matrix42
Calendar	Microsoft Exchange	SOGO	Horde Framework	Microfocus Groupwise	CommuniGate
LMS - Learning Management System	Moodle	Ilias	Stud.IP	OLAT	OPAL
Mail	Microsoft Exchange	Dovecot	GroupWise	CommuniGate	Zimbra
Project Management	GitLab	Jira	Microsoft Project	OpenProject	Redmine
Resource Management	HIS	SAP	Make	In-house development	GebMan
Sync and Share	NextCloud	OwnCloud	Seafile	Micro Focus Filr	Microsoft OneDrive
Ticket and incident management	OTRS	KIX Professional	Znuny	JIRA	Zammad
Event Management	Indico	Converia	cobra EventManager	ConfTool	HIS LSF
Video conferencing	Zoom	BigBlueButton	Microsoft Teams	Cisco WebEx	Jitsi
Video Management	OpenCast	Panopto	Vimp	MediaSite	Camtasia
Virtualization / IaaS	VMWare	Microsoft Hyper-V	Proxmox	OpenStack	Nutanix
Knowledge Management	Confluence	Microsoft SharePoint	Mediawiki	dokuwiki	Foswiki

Commercial license	Open source license	Hybrid license - open source and commercial
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Details of the participating facilities

Distribution of responses among countries (n=142)

Distribution of responses from Germany among the federal states (n=126)

Distribution among types of facilities (n=138).

Distribution across facility sizes (n=139).

Distribution of responses among countries (n=142)

Country	Quantity
Germany	130
Austria	7
Switzerland	5

Distribution of responses from Germany among the federal states (n=126)

State	Quantity
Thuringia	4
Schleswig-Holstein	2
Saxony-Anhalt	5
Saxony	12
Saarland	4
Rhineland-Palatinate	6
North Rhine Westphalia	19
Lower Saxony	13
Mecklenburg-Western Pomerania	2
Hesse	11
Hamburg	5
Bremen	2
Brandenburg	6
Berlin	9
Bavaria	11
Baden Württemberg	15

Distribution of responses by type of college (n=138).

Type	Quantity
University	82
University of Applied Sciences	46
Art / Music High School	4
State recognized private university	3
Other	1
Research facility	1
Church university	1

Distribution of responses by size of university (n=139).

Size	Quantity
More than 30,000	22
15,001 to 30,000	35
5,001 to 15,000	52
Up to 5.000	30

Results across all categories

Operating models and licenses

Graphics - Operating Models

Total operating models (n=1905)

Operating models by category (n=1905)

Distribution of operating models by category (n=1905)

Graphics - License models

Total license models (n=442)

License models by category (n=442)

Distribution of license models by category (n=442)

Tables - Operating Models

Total operating models (n=1905)

Operating models	Quantity
Operation on own servers on site by a service provider	30
Operation on own servers on site by us	1,424
Operation outside the university by a service provider	352
Operation outside the university by us	34
Operation partly by us, partly by a service provider	65

Details of the operation per category (n=1905)

Category	Operating model	Frequency
Backup	Operation on own servers on site by us	102
Backup	Operation outside the university by a service provider	3
Backup	Operation outside the university by us	2
Backup	Operation partly by us, partly by a service provider	7
Campus Management	Operation on own servers on site by a service provider	1
Campus Management	Operation on own servers on site by us	103
Campus Management	Operation outside the university by a service provider	6
Campus Management	Operation outside the university by us	4
Campus Management	Operation partly by us, partly by a service provider	11
Chat / Instant Messaging	Operation on own servers on site by a service provider	1
Chat / Instant Messaging	Operation on own servers on site by us	49
Chat / Instant Messaging	Operation outside the university by a service provider	54
Chat / Instant Messaging	Operation outside the university by us	5
Chat / Instant Messaging	Operation partly by us, partly by a service provider	6
Content management	Operation on own servers on site by a service provider	7
Content management	Operation on own servers on site by us	93
Content management	Operation outside the university by a service provider	12
Content management	Operation outside the university by us	2
Content management	Operation partly by us, partly by a service provider	8
Document Management System	Operation on own servers on site by a service provider	1
Document Management System	Operation on own servers on site by us	46
Document Management System	Operation outside the university by a service provider	3
Document Management System	Operation outside the university by us	1
Document Management System	Operation partly by us, partly by a service provider	3
Research Information System	Operation on own servers on site by a service provider	2
Research Information System	Operation on own servers on site by us	33
Research Information System	Operation outside the university by a service provider	5
Research Information System	Operation outside the university by us	1
IT Service Management	Operation on own servers on site by us	51
IT Service Management	Operation outside the university by a service provider	21
IT Service Management	Operation outside the university by us	1
IT Service Management	Operation partly by us, partly by a service provider	2
Calendar	Operation on own servers on site by a service provider	1
Calendar	Operation on own servers on site by us	75
Calendar	Operation outside the university by a service provider	9
Calendar	Operation outside the university by us	1
Calendar	Operation partly by us, partly by a service provider	3
LMS - Learning Management System	Operation on own servers on site by a service provider	4
LMS - Learning Management System	Operation on own servers on site by us	94
LMS - Learning Management System	Operation outside the university by a service provider	13
LMS - Learning Management System	Operation outside the university by us	3
LMS - Learning Management System	Operation partly by us, partly by a service provider	3
Mail	Operation on own servers on site by a service provider	1
Mail	Operation on own servers on site by us	92
Mail	Operation outside the university by a service provider	8
Mail	Operation outside the university by us	1
Mail	Operation partly by us, partly by a service provider	3
Project Management	Operation on own servers on site by a service provider	2
Project Management	Operation on own servers on site by us	103
Project Management	Operation outside the university by a service provider	16
Project Management	Operation partly by us, partly by a service provider	3
Resource Management	Operation on own servers on site by us	51
Resource Management	Operation outside the university by a service provider	21
Resource Management	Operation outside the university by us	1

Resource Management	Operation partly by us, partly by a service provider	2
Sync and Share	Operation on own servers on site by a service provider	1
Sync and Share	Operation on own servers on site by us	70
Sync and Share	Operation outside the university by a service provider	24
Sync and Share	Operation outside the university by us	1
Ticket and incident management	Operation on own servers on site by us	78
Ticket and incident management	Operation outside the university by a service provider	2
Event Management	Operation on own servers on site by us	78
Event Management	Operation outside the university by a service provider	2
Video conferencing	Operation on own servers on site by a service provider	5
Video conferencing	Operation on own servers on site by us	51
Video conferencing	Operation outside the university by a service provider	130
Video conferencing	Operation outside the university by us	5
Video conferencing	Operation partly by us, partly by a service provider	10
Video Management	Operation on own servers on site by a service provider	4
Video Management	Operation on own servers on site by us	41
Video Management	Operation outside the university by a service provider	11
Video Management	Operation outside the university by us	3
Video Management	Operation partly by us, partly by a service provider	3
Virtualization / IaaS	Operation on own servers on site by us	125
Virtualization / IaaS	Operation outside the university by us	1
Knowledge Management	Operation on own servers on site by us	89
Knowledge Management	Operation outside the university by a service provider	12
Knowledge Management	Operation outside the university by us	2
Knowledge Management	Operation partly by us, partly by a service provider	1

Tables - License models

Total license models (n=442)

License model	Quantity
Hybrid	51
Commercial	234
Open source	136
Self developed	21

License models per category (n=442)

Category	License model	Solution
Backup	Hybrid	1
Backup	Commercial	18
Backup	Open source	7
Backup	Self developed	3
Campus Management	Hybrid	7
Campus Management	Commercial	21
Campus Management	Open source	3
Campus Management	Self developed	3
Chat / Instant Messaging	Hybrid	2
Chat / Instant Messaging	Commercial	20
Chat / Instant Messaging	Open source	10
Content management	Hybrid	5
Content management	Commercial	14
Content management	Open source	11
Content management	Self developed	2
Document Management System	Hybrid	2
Document Management System	Commercial	14
Document Management System	Open source	1
Document Management System	Self developed	1
Research Information System	Hybrid	2
Research Information System	Commercial	8
Research Information System	Open source	4
Research Information System	Self developed	1
IT Service Management	Hybrid	2
IT Service Management	Commercial	10
IT Service Management	Open source	8
IT Service Management	Self developed	1
Calendar	Hybrid	3

Calendar	Commercial	9
Calendar	Open source	8
LMS - Learning Management System	Hybrid	5
LMS - Learning Management System	Commercial	7
LMS - Learning Management System	Open source	8
LMS - Learning Management System	Self developed	1
Mail	Hybrid	3
Mail	Commercial	10
Mail	Open source	18
Mail	Self developed	2
Project Management	Hybrid	4
Project Management	Commercial	12
Project Management	Open source	8
Resource Management	Hybrid	2
Resource Management	Commercial	14
Resource Management	Open source	6
Resource Management	Self developed	1
Sync and Share	Hybrid	5
Sync and Share	Commercial	10
Sync and Share	Open source	8
Sync and Share	Self developed	1
Ticket and incident management	Hybrid	4
Ticket and incident management	Commercial	12
Ticket and incident management	Open source	13
Ticket and incident management	Self developed	1
Event Management	Hybrid	1
Event Management	Commercial	13
Event Management	Open source	1
Event Management	Self developed	1
Video conferencing	Hybrid	1
Video conferencing	Commercial	10
Video conferencing	Open source	2
Video Management	Commercial	17
Video Management	Open source	4
Video Management	Self developed	3
Virtualization / IaaS	Hybrid	2
Virtualization / IaaS	Commercial	11
Virtualization / IaaS	Open source	8
Knowledge Management	Commercial	4
Knowledge Management	Open source	8

Category results

Backup

Summary of the results

Most frequent solutions in total (n=147)

Distribution by size of university (n=132)

Distribution by type of university sorted by solutions (n=132)

Distribution sorted by type of university (n=132)

Satisfaction with the solutions (n=78)

[Link for explanations of the boxplot](#)

Operating models of the solutions (n=114)

Individual tables of the evaluation
Frequencies of the solutions (n=177)

Solution	Quantity
ArcServ	1
Backup Express- DPX	1
Bacula	11
Bareos	1
Borg	1
Burp	1
code42 crashplan	1
CommVault	11
Data Backup.NRW (CommVault)	1
Dell EMC Integrated Data Protection Appliance	1
Dell EMC Networker	5
Proprietary developments	1
HP Dataprotector	1
https://www.nakivo.com/	1
IBM Spectrum Protect	46
Smaller decentralized systems	1
Legacy system with tape drives	1
Microfocus / HP Dataprotector	1
Microsoft Data Protection Manager	1
Netapp	4
proxmoxbackup	2
Quest netvault	1
rsync	1
Self-written backup scripts	1
Snapshot R Sync	1
Symantec Veritas Backup Exec	3
Synology Active Backup for Business	1
Time Navigator (TINA) from the Atempo company	1
Veeam	70
Veritas NetBackup	1
VMWare Snapshots	2
Windows Server Backup	1

Frequency of solutions in country mentions (n=132).

Country	Bacula	Dell EMC Networker	IBM Spectrum Protect	Veeam	SUM
Germany	11	4	44	64	123
Switzerland	0	1	2	4	7
Austria	0	0	0	2	2

Distribution of usage in relation to the number of students at the institution (n=132).

Size	Bacula	Dell EMC Networker	IBM Spectrum Protect	Veeam	SUM
Up to 5.000	4	1	4	16	25
5,001 to 15,000	5	2	12	32	51
15,001 to 30,000	0	2	18	15	35
More than 30,000	2	0	12	7	21

Distribution of use in relation to type of facility (n=132).

Type	Bacula	Dell EMC Networker	IBM Spectrum Protect	Veeam	SUM
University	4	2	38	37	81
University of Applied Sciences	5	3	7	28	43
Art / music high school	2	0	0	2	4
	0	0	1	0	1
Church university	0	0	0	1	1
Other	0	0	0	1	1
State recognized private university	0	0	0	1	1

How many solutions are used in parallel (n=103)

Number of solutions in operation	Number of mentions
1	74
2	29

Which combinations of solutions are used (n=29)

The table is understood row by row with statements of 'Yes' within the same row if the respective solutions are used in parallel.

Veeam	IBM Spectrum Protect	Dell EMC Networker	Bacula	Quantity
Yes	Yes	0	0	19
Yes	0	0	Yes	5
Yes	0	Yes	0	4
0	Yes	0	Yes	1

Overview of operating models and frequencies (n=114)

Solution	Operating model	Frequency
Bacula	Operation outside the university by a service provider	2
Bacula	Operation on own servers on site by us	9
Dell EMC Networker	Operation on own servers on site by us	5
IBM Spectrum Protect	Operation outside the university by a service provider	1
IBM Spectrum Protect	Operation partly by us, partly by a service provider	4
IBM Spectrum Protect	Operation on own servers on site by us	32
Veeam	Operation outside the university by us	2
Veeam	Operation partly by us, partly by a service provider	3
Veeam	Operation on own servers on site by us	56

Which license types are used (n=147)

Solution	License model
Proprietary developments	Self developed
Legacy system with tape drives	Self developed
Self-written backup scripts	Self developed
Bacula	Open source
Bareos	Open source
Borg	Open source
Burp	Open source
proxmoxbackup	Open Source
rsync	Open Source
VMWare Snapshots	Open Source
Backup Express- DPX	Commercial
Bacula	Commercial
code42 crashplan	Commercial
CommVault	Commercial
Data Backup.NRW (CommVault)	Commercial
Dell EMC Integrated Data Protection Appliance	Commercial
Dell EMC Networker	Commercial
HP Dataprotector	Commercial
IBM Spectrum Protect	Commercial
Microfocus / HP Dataprotector	Commercial
Microsoft Data Protection Manager	Commercial
Netapp	Commercial
Quest netvault	Commercial
Symantec Veritas Backup Exec	Commercial
Synology Active Backup for Business	Commercial
Time Navigator (TINA) from the Atempo company	Commercial
Veeam	Commercial
Veritas NetBackup	Commercial
Bacula	Hybrid

Satisfaction with the solutions (n=78)

Solution	Min	Lower quartile	Average	Median	Upper quartile	Max	Number of entries
Veeam	1.00	7.00	7.03	7.50	8.00	10.00	32.00
IBM Spectrum Protect	8.00	8.00	8.80	9.00	9.00	10.00	5.00
Dell EMC Networker	7.00	7.00	8.10	8.00	9.00	10.00	10.00
Bacula	1.00	6.00	7.13	8.00	9.00	10.00	31.00

Should the solution be replaced (n=13)

Solution	Intention to redeem
Veeam	5
IBM Spectrum Protect	8
Dell EMC Networker	0
Bacula	0

By what should the solution be weaned

Veeam	IBM Spectrum Protect
not yet fixed	CommVault (association with RWTH AC)
Data Backup.NRW (CommVault)	Data Backup.NRW (CommVault)
	Commvault
	commvault
	possibly Veeam

Campus Management System

Summary of the results

Most frequent solutions in total (n=142)

Distribution by size of university (n=132)

Distribution by type of university sorted by solutions (n=132)

Distribution sorted by type of university (n=132)

Satisfaction with the solutions (n=100)

[Link for explanations of the boxplot](#)

Operating models of the solutions (n=125)

Individual tables of the evaluation

Frequencies of the solutions (n=171)

Solution	Quantity
Academ	1
Academy Five	2
Application management MoveIn, PhD management Docata, exchange MoveOn, ...	1
CampusCore	1
CampusNet	17
CampusNet Apply	1
CAMPUSonline	7
CAS Campus	3
Docata (doctoral administration)	1
In-house development	1
Evento	1
fdsa	1
Flexnow	2
Flexnow (exam management)	1
HIS GX	48
HIS-QIS	1
HISinOne	62
IS-Academia from equinox	1
KSL	1
Primuss	3
SAP SLcM	8
Scientia S-Plus	2
StudIP	1
TraiNex	1
TUCaN	1
we are currently replacing HIS GX and CampusNet	1
We call it our SIS	1

Frequency of solutions in country mentions (n=132).

Country	Academy Five	CampusNet	HIS GX	HISinOne	Primuss	SUM
Germany	2	17	48	62	3	132

Distribution of usage in relation to the number of students at the institution (n=132).

Size	Academy Five	CampusNet	HIS GX	HISinOne	Primuss	SUM
Up to 5,000	1	6	9	13	1	30
5,001 to 15,000	1	4	22	30	2	59
15,001 to 30,000	0	3	12	15	0	30
More than 30,000	0	4	5	4	0	13

Distribution of use in relation to type of facility (n=132).

Type	Academy Five	CampusNet	HIS GX	HISinOne	Primuss	SUM
University of Applied Sciences	1	5	25	29	3	63
University	0	8	23	31	0	62
Art / music high school	0	1	0	2	0	3
State recognized private university	1	2	0	0	0	3
Church university	0	1	0	0	0	1

How many solutions are used in parallel (n=96)

Number of solutions in operation	Number of mentions
1	60
2	36

Which combinations of solutions are used (n=36)

The table is understood line by line with indications of 'Yes' within the same line if the respective solutions are used in parallel.

HISinOne	HIS GX	CampusNet	Academy Five	Primuss	Quantity
Yes	Yes	0	0	0	35
0	Yes	Yes	0	0	1

Overview of operating models and frequencies (n=125)

Solution	Operating model	Frequency
Academy Five	Operation outside the university by a service provider	1
Academy Five	Operation on own servers on site by us	1
CampusNet	Operation outside the university by us	1
CampusNet	Operation partly by us, partly by a service provider	1
CampusNet	Operation on own servers on site by us	14
HIS GX	Operation partly by us, partly by a service provider	4
HIS GX	Operation on own servers on site by us	43
HISinOne	Operation outside the university by a service provider	5
HISinOne	Operation outside the university by us	2
HISinOne	Operation partly by us, partly by a service provider	4
HISinOne	Operation on own servers on site by a service provider	1
HISinOne	Operation on own servers on site by us	45
Primuss	Operation outside the university by us	1
Primuss	Operation partly by us, partly by a service provider	2

Which license types are used (n=148)

Solution	License model
CAMPUSonline	Self developed
HISinOne	Self developed
Primuss	Self developed
CAMPUSonline	Open source
HIS GX	Open source
HISinOne	Open source
Academ	Commercial
Academy Five	Commercial
Application management MoveIn, PhD management Docata, exchange MoveOn, ...	Commercial
CampusCore	Commercial
CampusNet	Commercial
CampusNet Apply	Commercial
CAMPUSonline	Commercial
CAS Campus	Commercial
Docata (doctoral administration)	Commercial
In-house development	Commercial
Evento	Commercial
Flexnow	Commercial
Flexnow (exam management)	Commercial
HIS GX	Commercial
HISinOne	Commercial
IS-Academia from equinox	Commercial
KSL	Commercial
SAP SLcM	Commercial
Scientia S-Plus	Commercial
TraiNex	Commercial
we are currently replacing HIS GX and CampusNet	Commercial
CAMPUSonline	Hybrid
HIS GX	Hybrid
HIS-QIS	Hybrid
HISinOne	Hybrid
Primuss	Hybrid
Scientia S-Plus	Hybrid
We call it our SIS	Hybrid

Satisfaction with the solutions (n=100)

Solution	Min	Lower quartile	Average	Median	Upper quartile	Max	Number of entries
HISinOne	2.00	5.00	6.65	7.00	8.00	10.00	43.00
HIS GX	2.00	5.00	5.62	6.00	7.00	9.00	37.00
CampusNet	2.00	3.50	5.40	6.00	7.00	10.00	15.00
Academy Five	7.00	7.25	7.50	7.50	7.75	8.00	2.00
Primuss	8.00	8.50	9.00	9.00	9.50	10.00	3.00

Should the solution be replaced (n=36)

Solution	Intention to redeem
HISinOne	1
HIS GX	34
CampusNet	1
Academy Five	0
Primuss	0

By what should the solution be weaned

HISinOne	HIS GX	CampusNet
CampusNet	Will be gradually replaced by HISinOne	Campusnet Classic -> Campusnet NT
	SAP SLcM	
	HISinOne	
	HISinOne	
	CampusNet	
	HISinOne also for students and examination administration	
	HISinOne	
	is replaced by HISinOne	
	CampusOnline	

Chat / Instant Messaging

Summary of the results

Most frequent solutions in total (n=139)

Distribution according to size of university (n=125)

Distribution by type of college sorted by solutions (n=125).

Distribution sorted by type of university (n=125)

Satisfaction with the solutions (n=101)

[Link for explanations of the boxplot](#)

Operating models of the solutions (n=115)

Individual tables of the evaluation

Frequencies of the solutions (n=167)

Solution	Quantity
Alfaview	1
Big Blue Button	2
Cisco Jabber	4
Cisco Webex	20
ejabberd	1
GroupWise Messenger	1
Jabber	3
Matrix	22
Matrix	1
Mattermost	14
MiCollab	1
Microsoft Teams	46
pidgin	2
QTOX	1
Rainbow	1
RocketChat	23
Signal	2
Skype	1
Skype for Business	4
Slack	2
Starleaf Chat	1
Threema	1
Threema, Whatsapp, ...	1
WhatsApp	2
XMPP/Jabber	1
Zenkit Suite	1
Zoom	6
Zoom chat	1
Zulip	1

Frequency of solutions in country mentions (n=125).

Country	Cisco Webex	Matrix	Mattermost	Microsoft Teams	RocketChat	SUM
Germany	17	21	13	41	21	113
Switzerland	2	0	1	5	0	8
Austria	1	1	0	0	2	4

Distribution of usage in relation to the number of students at the institution (n=125).

Size	Cisco Webex	Matrix	Mattermost	Microsoft Teams	RocketChat	SUM
Up to 5.000	2	4	2	9	5	22
5,001 to 15,000	9	2	7	21	5	44
15,001 to 30,000	3	10	2	9	8	32
More than 30,000	6	6	3	7	5	27

Distribution of use in relation to type of facility (n=125).

Type	Cisco Webex	Matrix	Mattermost	Microsoft Teams	RocketChat	SUM
University	11	18	10	20	19	78
University of Applied Sciences	8	4	4	24	3	43
Art / music high school	1	0	0	0	1	2
State recognized private university	0	0	0	2	0	2

How many solutions are used in parallel (n=94)

Number of solutions in operation	Number of mentions
1	70
2	19
3	4
5	1

Which combinations of solutions are used (n=24)

The table is understood row by row with statements of 'Yes' within the same row if the respective solutions are used in parallel.

Microsoft Teams	RocketChat	Matrix	Mattermost	Cisco Webex	Quantity
Yes	0	0	Yes	0	6
Yes	Yes	0	0	0	5
0	0	Yes	0	Yes	2
Yes	0	0	0	Yes	2
Yes	0	Yes	0	0	2
0	0	0	Yes	Yes	1
0	0	Yes	Yes	Yes	1
0	Yes	0	0	Yes	1
0	Yes	Yes	0	Yes	1
Yes	Yes	0	0	Yes	1
Yes	Yes	Yes	0	0	1
Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	1

Overview of operating models and frequencies (n=115)

Solution	Operating model	Frequency
Cisco Webex	Operation outside the university by a service provider	11
Cisco Webex	Operation outside the university by us	2
Cisco Webex	Operation partly by us, partly by a service provider	3
Cisco Webex	Operation on own servers on site by a service provider	1
Cisco Webex	Operation on own servers on site by us	3
Matrix	Operation on own servers on site by us	20
Mattermost	Operation outside the university by a service provider	2
Mattermost	Operation outside the university by us	1
Mattermost	Operation partly by us, partly by a service provider	1
Mattermost	Operation on own servers on site by us	7
Microsoft Teams	Operation outside the university by a service provider	37
Microsoft Teams	Operation outside the university by us	2
Microsoft Teams	Operation partly by us, partly by a service provider	2
Microsoft Teams	Operation on own servers on site by us	2
RocketChat	Operation outside the university by a service provider	4
RocketChat	Operation on own servers on site by us	17

Which license types are used (n=156)

Solution	License model
Big Blue Button	Open source
ejabberd	Open source
Jabber	Open source
Matrix	Open source
Mattermost	Open source
pidgin	Open source
QTOX	Open source
RocketChat	Open source
Signal	Open source
XMPP/Jabber	Open source
Cisco Jabber	Commercial
Cisco Webex	Commercial
GroupWise Messenger	Commercial
Jabber	Commercial
Matrix	Commercial
Mattermost	Commercial
MiCollab	Commercial
Microsoft Teams	Commercial
Rainbow	Commercial
Signal	Commercial
Skype	Commercial
Skype for Business	Commercial
Slack	Commercial
Starleaf Chat	Commercial
Threema	Commercial
Threema, Whatsapp, ...	Commercial
WhatsApp	Commercial
Zenkit Suite	Commercial
Zoom	Commercial
Zoom chat	Commercial
Mattermost	Hybrid
RocketChat	Hybrid

Satisfaction with the solutions (n=101)

Solution	Min	Lower quartile	Average	Median	Upper quartile	Max	Number of entries
Microsoft Teams	1.00	8.00	8.05	8.00	9.00	10.00	38.00
RocketChat	5.00	7.00	8.00	8.00	9.00	10.00	21.00
Matrix	1.00	7.25	7.64	8.00	9.00	10.00	14.00
Mattermost	2.00	7.00	7.56	8.00	9.00	10.00	9.00
Cisco Webex	2.00	7.00	7.63	8.00	8.50	10.00	19.00

Should the solution be replaced (n=10)

Solution	Intention to redeem
Microsoft Teams	0
RocketChat	5
Matrix	1
Mattermost	2
Cisco Webex	2

By what should the solution be weaned

RocketChat	Matrix	Mattermost	Cisco Webex
decentralized installations, consolidation is the order of the day here.	decentralized installations, consolidation is the order of the day here.	decentralized installations, consolidation is the order of the day here.	Only a few remaining licenses
Matrix		is to be replaced by MS Teams	MS Teams, zoom
is still under construction			

CMS - Content Management System

Summary of the results

Most frequent solutions in total (n=132)

Distribution by size of university (n=128)

Distribution by type of university sorted by solutions (n=128)

Distribution sorted by type of university (n=128)

Satisfaction with the solutions (n=101)

[Link for explanations of the boxplot](#)

Operating models of the solutions (n=122)

Individual tables of the evaluation

Frequencies of the solutions (n=156)

Solution	Quantity
CMS Fiona of the company JustRelate	1
Drupal	8
EgoCMS	1
EgoTec	2
Fiona	2
FIONA/Scrivito	1
FirstSpirit	4
Imperia	4
joomla	1
Liferay	1
Magic (proprietary development)	1
Microsoft Sharepoint	2
OpenCms	1
OpenText WSM	2
Pimcore	1
Plone	8
Sidecore	1
Sitepark Infosite 6	1
Sitepark Infosite EE	1
Static Webpages (CI generated)	1
Synfo	1
Typo3	79
Umbraco	1
Wordpress	29
DMF	2

Frequency of solutions in country mentions (n=128).

Country	Drupal	Imperia	Plone	Typo3	Wordpress	SUM
Germany	8	4	8	73	27	120
Austria	0	0	0	3	2	5
Switzerland	0	0	0	3	0	3

Distribution of usage in relation to the number of students at the institution (n=128).

Size	Drupal	Imperia	Plone	Typo3	Wordpress	SUM
Up to 5,000	3	0	0	19	6	28
5,001 to 15,000	3	1	2	37	11	54
15,001 to 30,000	0	1	5	17	5	28
More than 30,000	2	2	1	6	7	18

Distribution of use in relation to type of facility (n=128).

Type	Drupal	Imperia	Plone	Typo3	Wordpress	SUM
University	3	2	7	40	16	68
University of Applied Sciences	5	2	1	34	12	54
State recognized private university	0	0	0	2	1	3
Art / Music High School	0	0	0	2	0	2
Church university	0	0	0	1	0	1

How many solutions are used in parallel (n=95)

Number of solutions in operation	Number of mentions
1	67
2	23
3	5

Which combinations of the solutions are used (n=28)

The table is understood line by line with indications of 'Yes' within the same line if the respective solutions are used in parallel.

Typo3	Plone	Imperia	Wordpress	Drupal	Quantity
Yes	0	0	Yes	0	14
Yes	0	0	Yes	Yes	3
Yes	Yes	0	0	0	3
0	0	Yes	Yes	0	2
0	Yes	0	Yes	0	2
0	0	0	Yes	Yes	1
0	0	Yes	Yes	Yes	1
Yes	0	Yes	0	0	1
Yes	Yes	0	Yes	0	1

Overview of operating models and frequencies (n=122)

Solution	Operating model	Frequency
Drupal	Operation on own servers on site by a service provider	2
Drupal	Operation on own servers on site by us	5
Imperia	Operation on own servers on site by us	4
Plone	Operation on own servers on site by a service provider	1
Plone	Operation on own servers on site by us	7
Typo3	Operation outside the university by a service provider	10
Typo3	Operation outside the university by us	2
Typo3	Operation partly by us, partly by a service provider	4
Typo3	Operation on own servers on site by a service provider	4
Typo3	Operation on own servers on site by us	56
Wordpress	Operation outside the university by a service provider	2
Wordpress	Operation partly by us, partly by a service provider	4
Wordpress	Operation on own servers on site by us	21

Which license types are used (n=145)

Solution	License model
Magic (proprietary development)	Self developed
Typo3	Self developed
Drupal	Open source
joomla	Open source
Liferay	Open Source
OpenCms	Open source
Pimcore	Open source
Plone	Open source
Static Webpages (CI generated)	Open source
Typo3	Open source
Umbraco	Open source
Wordpress	Open source
DMF	Open source
CMS Fiona of the company JustRelate	Commercial
Drupal	Commercial
EgoCMS	Commercial
EgoTec	Commercial
Fiona	Commercial
FIONA/Scrivito	Commercial
FirstSpirit	Commercial
Imperia	Commercial
Microsoft Sharepoint	Commercial
OpenText WSM	Commercial
Sitepark Infosite 6	Commercial
Sitepark Infosite EE	Commercial
Typo3	Commercial
Wordpress	Commercial
Imperia	Hybrid
Plone	Hybrid
Synfo	Hybrid
Typo3	Hybrid
Wordpress	Hybrid

Satisfaction with the solutions (n=101)

Solution	Min	Lower quartile	Average	Median	Upper quartile	Max	Number of entries
Typo3	1.00	7.00	7.18	7.50	8.00	10.00	66.00
Plone	5.00	6.00	6.40	7.00	7.00	7.00	5.00
Imperia	6.00	6.75	7.75	8.00	9.00	9.00	4.00
Wordpress	2.00	7.00	7.55	8.00	8.25	10.00	20.00
Drupal	3.00	4.00	6.17	7.50	8.00	8.00	6.00

Should the solution be replaced (n=8)

Solution	Intention to redeem
Typo3	0
Plone	3
Imperia	1
Wordpress	1
Drupal	3

By what should the solution be weaned

Plone	Imperia	Wordpress	Drupal
Replacement with Wordpress	Typo3	but is not intended as a university-wide standard and is to be replaced	but is not intended as a university-wide standard and is to be replaced
Typo3			Change of service provider if necessary
			higher Drupal version

DMS - Document Management System

Summary of the results

Most frequent solutions in total (n=62)

Distribution by size of university (n=63)

Distribution by type of university sorted by solutions (n=63)

Distribution sorted by type of university (n=63)

Satisfaction with the solutions (n=39)

[Link for explanations of the boxplot](#)

Operating models of the solutions (n=54)

Individual tables of the evaluation

Frequencies of the solutions (n=81)

Solution	Quantity
Aconso	1
Alfresco	6
Codia d.3	48
d.velop	2
DocuWare	4
Doxis 4	2
EasyArchive	1
ELO Digital Office	3
Photoware	1
inPuncto	1
Kendox	1
Lib-IT Filero	4
MACH Workflow (based on Alfresco)	1
Nextcloud addon	1
SAP folder management	1
SharePoint	3
Sharepoint solution with workflow addons, developed by DL	1

Frequency of solutions in country mentions (n=63).

Country	Alfresco	Codia d.3	Doxis 4	ELO Digital Office	Lib-IT Filero	SUM
Germany	6	48	2	3	4	63

Distribution of usage in relation to the number of students at the institution (n=63).

Size	Alfresco	Codia d.3	Doxis 4	ELO Digital Office	Lib-IT Filero	SUM
Up to 5.000	1	7	0	0	1	9
5,001 to 15,000	4	25	1	2	3	35
15,001 to 30,000	0	11	1	0	0	12
More than 30,000	1	5	0	1	0	7

Distribution of use in relation to type of facility (n=63).

Type	Alfresco	Codia d.3	Doxis 4	ELO Digital Office	Lib-IT Filero	SUM
University of Applied Sciences	3	26	0	1	4	34
University	3	20	2	2	0	27
Art / Music High School	0	1	0	0	0	1
State recognized private university	0	1	0	0	0	1

How many solutions are used in parallel (n=58)

Number of solutions in operation	Number of mentions
1	53
2	5

Which combinations of the solutions are used (n=5)

The table is understood line by line with indications of 'Yes' within the same line if the respective solutions are used in parallel.

Codia d.3	Lib-IT Filero	ELO Digital Office	Alfresco	Doxis 4	Quantity
Yes	0	0	Yes	0	2
0	0	Yes	Yes	0	1
Yes	0	Yes	0	0	1
Yes	Yes	0	0	0	1

Overview of operating models and frequencies (n=54)

Solution	Operating model	Frequency
Alfresco	Operation on own servers on site by us	6
Codia d.3	Operation outside the university by a service provider	1
Codia d.3	Operation outside the university by us	1
Codia d.3	Operation partly by us, partly by a service provider	2
Codia d.3	Operation on own servers on site by us	36
Doxis 4	Operation on own servers on site by us	1
ELO Digital Office	Operation on own servers on site by a service provider	1
ELO Digital Office	Operation on own servers on site by us	2
Lib-IT Filero	Operation outside the university by a service provider	2
Lib-IT Filero	Operation partly by us, partly by a service provider	1
Lib-IT Filero	Operation on own servers on site by us	1

Which license types are used (n=74)

Solution	License model
Nextcloud addon	Self developed
Alfresco	Open source
Aconso	Commercial
Codia d.3	Commercial
d.velop	Commercial
DocuWare	Commercial
Doxis 4	Commercial
EasyArchive	Commercial
ELO Digital Office	Commercial
Photoware	Commercial
inPuncto	Commercial
Kendox	Commercial
Lib-IT Filero	Commercial
MACH Workflow (based on Alfresco)	Commercial
SAP folder management	Commercial
SharePoint	Commercial
Alfresco	Hybrid
Sharepoint solution with workflow addons, developed by DL	Hybrid

Satisfaction with the solutions (n=39)

Solution	Min	Lower quartile	Average	Median	Upper quartile	Max	Number of entries
Codia d.3	1.00	5.75	6.00	6.50	8.00	9.00	28.00
Lib-IT Filero	3.00	3.00	4.33	3.00	5.00	7.00	3.00
ELO Digital Office	7.00	7.25	7.50	7.50	7.75	8.00	2.00
Alfresco	3.00	5.00	5.40	5.00	6.00	8.00	5.00
Doxis 4	2.00	2.00	2.00	2.00	2.00	2.00	1.00

Should the solution be replaced (n=9)

Solution	Intention to redeem
Codia d.3	4
Lib-IT Filero	0
ELO Digital Office	1
Alfresco	4
Doxis 4	0

By what should the solution be weaned

Codia d.3	ELO Digital Office	Alfresco
unclear	Codia.d3	Codia d.3
Yes, renaming to d.velop documents		Tender in preparation
under review		

FIS - Research Information System

Summary of the results

Most frequent solutions in total (n=49)

Distribution by size of university (n=49)

Distribution by type of university sorted by solutions (n=49)

Distribution sorted by type of university (n=49)

Satisfaction with the solutions (n=30)

[Link for explanations of the boxplot](#)

Operating models of the solutions (n=41)

Individual tables of the evaluation

Frequencies of the solutions (n=61)

Solution	Quantity
BayFIS	1
Clarivate Converis	7
DSpace	1
DSpace-CRIS	2
In-house development	1
In-house development	17
Elsevier Pure	7
FACTScience of QLEO Science GmbH	1
Research database based on HIS LSF	1
HISinOne-RES	18
Jira (Customized)	1
Matching Needs	1
MS Access based solution	1
ViVo	2

Frequency of solutions in country mentions (n=49).

Country	Clarivate Converis	In-house development	Elsevier Pure	HISinOne-RES	SUM
Germany	7	15	5	18	45
Switzerland	0	2	0	0	2
Austria	0	0	2	0	2

Distribution of usage in relation to the number of students at the institution (n=49).

Size	Clarivate Converis	In-house development	Elsevier Pure	HISinOne-RES	SUM
Up to 5.000	0	4	1	5	10
5,001 to 15,000	1	9	1	9	20
15,001 to 30,000	3	2	3	4	12
More than 30,000	3	2	2	0	7

Distribution of use in relation to type of facility (n=49).

Type	Clarivate Converis	In-house development	Elsevier Pure	HISinOne-RES	SUM
University	7	8	7	6	28
University of Applied Sciences	0	9	0	11	20
Art / Music High School	0	0	0	1	1

How many solutions are used in parallel (n=46)

Number of solutions in operation	Number of mentions
1	43
2	3

Which combinations of the solutions are used (n=3)

The table is understood line by line with indications of 'Yes' within the same line if the respective solutions are used in parallel.

HISinOne-RES	In-house development	Clarivate Converis	Elsevier Pure	Quantity
Yes	Yes	0	0	2
Yes	0	Yes	0	1

Overview of operating models and frequencies (n=41)

Solution	Operating model	Frequency
Clarivate Converis	Operation on own servers on site by a service provider	2
Clarivate Converis	Operation on own servers on site by us	4
In-house development	Operation on own servers on site by us	14
Elsevier Pure	Operation outside the university by a service provider	1
Elsevier Pure	Operation on own servers on site by us	4
HISinOne-RES	Operation outside the university by a service provider	4
HISinOne-RES	Operation outside the university by us	1
HISinOne-RES	Operation on own servers on site by us	11

Which license types are used (n=53)

Solution	License model
In-house development	Self developed
DSpace	Open source
DSpace-CRIS	Open source
In-house development	Open source
ViVo	Open source
Clarivate Converis	Commercial
Elsevier Pure	Commercial
FACTScience of QLEO Science GmbH	Commercial
Research database based on HIS LSF	Commercial
HISinOne-RES	Commercial
Jira (Customized)	Commercial
Matching Needs	Commercial
MS Access based solution	Commercial
In-house development	Hybrid
HISinOne-RES	Hybrid

Satisfaction with the solutions (n=30)

Solution	Min	Lower quartile	Average	Median	Upper quartile	Max	Number of entries
HISinOne-RES	5.00	5.00	6.33	5.50	8.00	9.00	12.00
In-house development	5.00	5.75	6.25	6.50	7.00	7.00	4.00
Clarivate Converis	3.00	6.00	6.80	8.00	8.00	9.00	5.00
Elsevier Pure	3.00	5.00	6.56	6.00	8.00	9.00	9.00

Should the solution be replaced (n=6)

Solution	Intention to redeem
HISinOne-RES	0
In-house development	4
Clarivate Converis	1
Elsevier Pure	1

By what should the solution be weaned

In-house development	Clarivate Converis	Elsevier Pure
New development of FIS components and connectors	HISinOne-RES	HISinOne FIS
HISinOne-RES	Possibly change to HISinOne-Res	
???		

IT Service Management

Summary of the results

Individual tables of the evaluation

Frequencies of the solutions:

Solution	Quantity
Echolon	1
In-house development	2
Helpline	1
i-doit	14
Ivanti	1
JIRA Service Management	10
KIX	4
Ky2Help	1
Matrix42	3
OS ticket	1
OTOBO	1
OTRS	3
OTRS/Znuny	2
Service Now	1
TOPdesk	4
Zammad	1
Znuny	1
Znuny (OTRS)	1

Type of licenses

Solution	License model
KIX	Open source
OS ticket	Open source
OTOBO	Open source
OTRS	Open source
OTRS/Znuny	Open source
Zammad	Open source
Znuny	Open Source
i-doit	Open Source
KIX	Hybrid
i-doit	Hybrid
Echolon	Commercial
Helpline	Commercial
Ivanti	Commercial
JIRA Service Management	Commercial
KIX	Commercial
Ky2Help	Commercial
Matrix42	Commercial
Service Now	Commercial
TOPdesk	Commercial
i-doit	Commercial
In-house development	Self developed

Calendar

Summary of the results

Most frequent solutions in total (n=114)

Distribution according to size of university (n=96)

Distribution by type of college sorted by solutions (n=96).

Distribution sorted by type of university (n=96)

Satisfaction with the solutions (n=38)

[Link for explanations of the boxplot](#)

Operating models of the solutions (n=89)

Individual tables of the evaluation

Frequencies of the solutions (n=127)

Solution	Quantity
Bedework	1
Communigate	4
Davical	1
Domino Notes	1
eGroupware	3
ExchangeOnline	2
Groupware	1
Horde Framework	7
Kerio Connect	1
Microfocus Groupwise	7
Microsoft Exchange	79
Nextcloud	4
OpenXchange	1
Oracle Beehive	1
SOGGo	9
Tine	1
Zimbra	4

Frequency of solutions in country mentions (n=96).

Country	Microfocus Groupwise	Microsoft Exchange	SOGGo	Tine	SUM
Germany	7	72	9	1	89
Switzerland	0	5	0	0	5
Austria	0	2	0	0	2

Distribution of usage in relation to the number of students at the institution (n=96).

Size	Microfocus Groupwise	Microsoft Exchange	SOGGo	Tine	SUM
Up to 5,000	2	16	2	0	20
5,001 to 15,000	2	28	4	1	35
15,001 to 30,000	3	22	1	0	26
More than 30,000	0	13	2	0	15

Distribution of use in relation to type of facility (n=96).

Type	Microfocus Groupwise	Microsoft Exchange	SOGGo	Tine	SUM
University	2	47	7	0	56
University of Applied Sciences	5	29	2	1	37
State recognized private university	0	2	0	0	2
Church university	0	1	0	0	1

How many solutions are used in parallel (n=93)

Number of solutions in operation	Number of mentions
1	90
2	3

Which combinations of the solutions are used (n=3)

The table is understood line by line with indications of 'Yes' within the same line if the respective solutions are used in parallel.

Microsoft Exchange	SOGo	Microfocus Groupwise	Tine	Quantity
Yes	Yes	0	0	3

Overview of operating models and frequencies (n=89)

Solution	Operating model	Frequency
Microfocus Groupwise	Operation on own servers on site by us	6
Microsoft Exchange	Operation outside the university by a service provider	8
Microsoft Exchange	Operation outside the university by us	1
Microsoft Exchange	Operation partly by us, partly by a service provider	3
Microsoft Exchange	Operation on own servers on site by a service provider	1
Microsoft Exchange	Operation on own servers on site by us	60
SOGo	Operation outside the university by a service provider	1
SOGo	Operation on own servers on site by us	8
Tine	Operation on own servers on site by us	1

Which license types are used (n=120)

Solution	License model
Bedework	Open source
Davical	Open source
eGroupware	Open source
Horde Framework	Open source
Nextcloud	Open source
SOGo	Open Source
Tine	Open Source
Zimbra	Open source
Communigate	Commercial
Domino Notes	Commercial
eGroupware	Commercial
ExchangeOnline	Commercial
Kerio Connect	Commercial
Microfocus Groupwise	Commercial
Microsoft Exchange	Commercial
OpenXchange	Commercial
Oracle Beehive	Commercial
eGroupware	Hybrid
SOGo	Hybrid
Zimbra	Hybrid

Satisfaction with the solutions (n=38)

Solution	Min	Lower quartile	Average	Median	Upper quartile	Max	Number of entries
Microsoft Exchange	6.00	6.50	7.29	7.00	8.00	9.00	7.00
SOGGo	3.00	5.00	6.17	6.00	7.75	9.00	6.00
Microfocus Groupwise	6.00	6.00	6.00	6.00	6.00	6.00	1.00
Tine	2.00	4.00	6.00	7.00	8.00	9.00	24.00

Should the solution be replaced (n=5)

Solution	Intention to redeem
Microsoft Exchange	5
SOGGo	0
Microfocus Groupwise	0
Tine	0

By what should the solution be weaned

Microsoft Exchange
possibly through Open-Xchange
Microsoft Exchange Online
Exchange Online
Migration before "end of life" to a non-Microsoft solution
Still unclear, switch becomes more likely with compulsion to cloud
Dovecot

LMS - Learning Management System

Summary of the results

Most frequent solutions in total (n=123)

Distribution by size of university (n=123)

Distribution by type of university sorted by solutions (n=123)

Distribution sorted by type of university (n=123)

Satisfaction with the solutions (n=100)

[Link for explanations of the boxplot](#)

Operating models of the solutions (n=117)

Individual tables of the evaluation

Frequencies of the solutions (n=131)

Solution	Quantity
Blackboard	1
C3LLO	1
Canvas	1
CommSy	1
Ilias	28
Moodle	67
MS Teams	1
OLAT	8
OPAL	6
OpenOlat	1
Sakai	1
Stud.IP	14
TraiNex integrated	1

Frequency of solutions in country mentions (n=123).

Country	Ilias	Moodle	OLAT	OPAL	Stud.IP	SUM
Germany	27	62	7	6	14	116
Switzerland	1	3	1	0	0	5
Austria	0	2	0	0	0	2

Distribution of usage in relation to the number of students at the institution (n=123).

Size	Ilias	Moodle	OLAT	OPAL	Stud.IP	SUM
Up to 5.000	3	17	1	4	2	27
5,001 to 15,000	8	29	4	1	5	47
15,001 to 30,000	12	13	1	0	6	32
More than 30,000	5	8	2	1	1	17

Distribution of use in relation to type of facility (n=123).

Type	Ilias	Moodle	OLAT	OPAL	Stud.IP	SUM
University	18	31	5	3	10	67
University of Applied Sciences	10	32	2	3	4	51
Art / music high school	0	2	0	0	0	2
State recognized private university	0	2	0	0	0	2
Church university	0	0	1	0	0	1

How many solutions are used in parallel (n=103)

Number of solutions in operation	Number of mentions
1	86
2	14
3	3

Which combinations of solutions are used (n=17)

The table is understood row by row with statements of 'Yes' within the same row if the respective solutions are used in parallel.

Moodle	Ilias	Stud.IP	OPAL	OLAT	Quantity
0	Yes	Yes	0	0	4
Yes	0	Yes	0	0	3
Yes	Yes	0	0	0	3
Yes	0	0	0	Yes	2
Yes	0	0	Yes	0	2
Yes	Yes	Yes	0	0	2
Yes	Yes	0	Yes	0	1

Overview of operating models and frequencies (n=117)

Solution	Operating model	Frequency
Ilias	Operation outside the university by us	1
Ilias	Operation partly by us, partly by a service provider	1
Ilias	Operation on own servers on site by us	25
Moodle	Operation outside the university by a service provider	6
Moodle	Operation outside the university by us	2
Moodle	Operation on own servers on site by a service provider	3
Moodle	Operation on own servers on site by us	55
OLAT	Operation outside the university by a service provider	3
OLAT	Operation on own servers on site by us	4
OPAL	Operation outside the university by a service provider	4
OPAL	Operation on own servers on site by us	1
Stud.IP	Operation partly by us, partly by a service provider	2
Stud.IP	Operation on own servers on site by a service provider	1
Stud.IP	Operation on own servers on site by us	9

Which license types are used (n=120)

Solution	License model
C3LLO	Self developed
CommSy	Open source
Ilias	Open source
Moodle	Open source
OLAT	Open source
OPAL	Open source
OpenOlat	Open source
Sakai	Open source
Stud.IP	Open source
Blackboard	Commercial
Canvas	Commercial
Ilias	Commercial
Moodle	Commercial
MS Teams	Commercial
OPAL	Commercial
TraiNex integrated	Commercial
Ilias	Hybrid
Moodle	Hybrid
OLAT	Hybrid
OPAL	Hybrid
Stud.IP	Hybrid

Satisfaction with the solutions (n=100)

Solution	Min	Lower quartile	Average	Median	Upper quartile	Max	Number of entries
Moodle	1.00	8.00	8.05	8.00	9.00	10.00	58.00
Ilias	2.00	7.00	7.30	8.00	8.00	10.00	20.00
Stud.IP	2.00	6.50	7.45	8.00	9.00	10.00	11.00
OPAL	5.00	7.00	7.00	7.00	8.00	8.00	5.00
OLAT	7.00	7.25	8.00	8.00	8.75	9.00	6.00

Should the solution be replaced (n=1)

Solution	Intention to redeem
Moodle	0
Ilias	0
Stud.IP	1
OPAL	0
OLAT	0

By what should the solution be weaned

Stud.IP
OpenOlat

Mail

Summary of the results

Most frequent solutions in total (n=124)

Distribution by size of university (n=116)

Distribution by type of college sorted by solutions (n=116).

Distribution sorted by type of university (n=116)

Satisfaction with the solutions (n=97)

[Link for explanations of the boxplot](#)

Operating models of the solutions (n=105)

Individual tables of the evaluation
Frequencies of the solutions (n=152)

Solution	Quantity
CommuniGate	4
Cyrus	3
cyrus	1
Domino Notes	1
Dovecot	1
Dovecot	28
ExchangeOnline	1
Exim	3
GroupWise	7
Hermes	1
Horde	3
HORDE/UWIMAP	1
Kerio Connect	1
Microsoft Exchange	81
OpenXchange	1
Oracle Beehive	1
PerMail	1
postfix	1
Postfix	2
Postfix/Cyrus	1
SOGoo	1
SquirrelMail	1
SUN Convergence	1
Unix SMTP	1
webmail/horde groupmail	1
Zimbra	4

Frequency of solutions in country mentions (n=116).

Country	Dovecot	GroupWise	Microsoft Exchange	SUM
Germany	26	7	74	107
Switzerland	0	0	5	5
Austria	2	0	2	4

Distribution of usage in relation to the number of students at the institution (n=116).

Size	Dovecot	GroupWise	Microsoft Exchange	SUM
Up to 5,000	4	2	16	22
5,001 to 15,000	13	2	28	43
15,001 to 30,000	6	3	24	33
More than 30,000	5	0	13	18

Distribution of use in relation to type of facility (n=116).

Type	Dovecot	GroupWise	Microsoft Exchange	SUM
University	18	2	49	69
University of Applied Sciences	9	5	29	43
State recognized private university	0	0	2	2
Church university	0	0	1	1
Art / music high school	1	0	0	1

How many solutions are used in parallel (n=101)

Number of solutions in operation	Number of mentions
1	86
2	15

Which combinations of the solutions are used (n=15)

The table is understood line by line with indications of 'Yes' within the same line if the respective solutions are used in parallel.

Microsoft Exchange	Dovecot	GroupWise	Quantity
Yes	Yes	0	15

Overview of operating models and frequencies (n=105)

Solution	Operating model	Frequency
Dovecot	Operation on own servers on site by us	25
GroupWise	Operation on own servers on site by us	6
Microsoft Exchange	Operation outside the university by a service provider	8
Microsoft Exchange	Operation outside the university by us	1
Microsoft Exchange	Operation partly by us, partly by a service provider	3
Microsoft Exchange	Operation on own servers on site by a service provider	1
Microsoft Exchange	Operation on own servers on site by us	61

Which license types are used (n=153)

Solution	License model
C3LLO	Self developed
PerMail	Self developed
CommSy	Open source
cyrus	Open source
Cyrus	Open source
Dovecot	Open source
Exim	Open source
Hermes	Open Source
Horde	Open source
OLAT	Open source
OpenOlat	Open source
OpenXchange	Open source
postfix	Open source
Postfix	Open source
Postfix/Cyrus	Open source
Sakai	Open source
SquirrelMail	Open source
Unix SMTP	Open source
webmail/horde groupmail	Open Source
Zimbra	Open Source
Blackboard	Commercial
Canvas	Commercial
CommuniGate	Commercial
GroupWise	Commercial
Kerio Connect	Commercial
Microsoft Exchange	Commercial
MS Teams	Commercial
Oracle Beehive	Commercial
SUN Convergence	Commercial
TraiNex integrated	Commercial
Horde	Hybrid
OLAT	Hybrid
Zimbra	Hybrid

Satisfaction with the solutions (n=97)

Solution	Min	Lower quartile	Average	Median	Upper quartile	Max	Number of entries
Microsoft Exchange	2.00	7.00	7.81	8.00	9.00	10.00	69.00
Dovecot	1.00	8.00	8.27	9.00	9.00	10.00	22.00
GroupWise	3.00	5.00	6.00	6.00	7.75	8.00	6.00

Should the solution be replaced (n=6)

Solution	Intention to redeem
Microsoft Exchange	5
Dovecot	1
GroupWise	0

By what should the solution be weaned

Microsoft Exchange	Dovecot
Microsoft Exchange Online	Exchange (online)
Exchange Online	
Migration before "end of life" to a non-Microsoft solution	
Change likely in transition to Azure cloud	

Project Management

Summary of the results

Most frequent solutions in total (n=139)

Distribution by size of university (n=139)

Distribution by type of university sorted by solutions (n=139)

Distribution sorted by type of university (n=139)

Satisfaction with the solutions (n=99)

[Link for explanations of the boxplot](#)

Operating models of the solutions (n=124)

Individual tables of the evaluation

Frequencies of the solutions (n=155)

Solution	Quantity
ActiveCollab	1
GitLab	58
Jira	27
Kanban Board	1
kanboard	1
Matrix42	1
mastertask	1
Microsoft Project	26
MS Planner	1
ONLYOFFICE	1
OpenProject	16
Plan.io (Commercial product based on Redmine)	1
Planta	1
ProjectLibre	2
Redmine	12
Service Now	1
Stackfield	1
Visual Paradigm	1
Wekan	1
Zenkit Suite	1

Frequency of solutions in country mentions (n=139).

Country	GitLab	Jira	Microsoft Project	OpenProject	Redmine	SUM
Germany	54	21	22	16	12	125
Switzerland	2	4	4	0	0	10
Austria	2	2	0	0	0	4

Distribution of usage in relation to the number of students at the institution (n=139).

Size	GitLab	Jira	Microsoft Project	OpenProject	Redmine	SUM
Up to 5.000	5	4	7	3	1	20
5,001 to 15,000	21	10	11	6	3	51
15,001 to 30,000	20	10	4	2	6	42
More than 30,000	12	3	4	5	2	26

Distribution of use in relation to type of facility (n=139).

Type	GitLab	Jira	Microsoft Project	OpenProject	Redmine	SUM
University	40	13	15	11	9	88
University of Applied Sciences	18	13	10	4	3	48
Church university	0	1	0	0	0	1
Art / Music High School	0	0	0	1	0	1
State recognized private university	0	0	1	0	0	1

How many solutions are used in parallel (n=88)

Number of solutions in operation	Number of mentions
1	53
2	21
3	12
4	2

Which combinations of the solutions are used (n=35)

The table is understood line by line with indications of 'Yes' within the same line if the respective solutions are used in parallel.

GitLab	Jira	OpenProject	Microsoft Project	Redmine	Quantity
Yes	0	0	Yes	0	6
Yes	0	Yes	0	0	5
Yes	Yes	0	0	0	5
Yes	Yes	0	Yes	0	4
0	Yes	0	Yes	0	3
Yes	0	Yes	Yes	0	3
Yes	0	0	0	Yes	2
Yes	0	0	Yes	Yes	2
Yes	0	Yes	0	Yes	2
Yes	Yes	0	0	Yes	1
Yes	Yes	Yes	0	Yes	1
Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	0	1

Overview of operating models and frequencies (n=124)

Solution	Operating model	Frequency
GitLab	Operation outside the university by a service provider	5
GitLab	Operation partly by us, partly by a service provider	1
GitLab	Operation on own servers on site by a service provider	1
GitLab	Operation on own servers on site by us	46
Jira	Operation outside the university by a service provider	3
Jira	Operation on own servers on site by us	24
Microsoft Project	Operation outside the university by a service provider	5
Microsoft Project	Operation partly by us, partly by a service provider	1
Microsoft Project	Operation on own servers on site by us	13
OpenProject	Operation outside the university by a service provider	3
OpenProject	Operation partly by us, partly by a service provider	1
OpenProject	Operation on own servers on site by a service provider	1
OpenProject	Operation on own servers on site by us	10
Redmine	Operation on own servers on site by us	10

Which license types are used (n=138)

Solution	License model
GitLab	Open source
Jira	Open source
Kanban Board	Open source
kanboard	Open source
OpenProject	Open source
ProjectLibre	Open source
Redmine	Open source
Wekan	Open source
GitLab	Commercial
Jira	Commercial
Matrix42	Commercial
Microsoft Project	Commercial
MS Planner	Commercial
ONLYOFFICE	Commercial
OpenProject	Commercial
Planta	Commercial
Service Now	Commercial
Stackfield	Commercial
Visual Paradigm	Commercial
Zenkit Suite	Commercial
GitLab	Hybrid
Jira	Hybrid
OpenProject	Hybrid
Plan.io (Commercial product based on Redmine)	Hybrid

Satisfaction with the solutions (n=99)

Solution	Min	Lower quartile	Average	Median	Upper quartile	Max	Number of entries
GitLab	1.00	8.00	8.24	8.00	9.00	10.00	41.00
Jira	4.00	7.00	7.84	8.00	9.00	10.00	25.00
OpenProject	2.00	7.00	7.11	8.00	8.00	9.00	9.00
Microsoft Project	3.00	6.25	6.94	7.00	8.00	9.00	18.00
Redmine	1.00	4.50	5.67	6.50	7.75	8.00	6.00

Should the solution be replaced (n=6)

Solution	Intention to redeem
GitLab	0
Jira	3
OpenProject	0
Microsoft Project	2
Redmine	1

By what should the solution be weaned

Jira	Microsoft Project	Redmine
Migration to the Jira cloud solution if necessary	Not yet clear	OpenProject
GitLab	ProjectLibre and if necessary OpenProject	

Resource Management

Summary of the results

Most frequent solutions in total (n=84)

Distribution according to size of university (n=84)

Distribution by type of college sorted by solutions (n=84).

Distribution by type of college sorted by type (n=84).

Satisfaction with the solutions (n=64)

Zufriedenheit mit der Lösung von 1 - sehr unzufrieden bis 10 - sehr zufrieden

[Link for explanations of the boxplot](#)

Operating models of the solutions (n=75)

Individual tables of the evaluation

Frequencies of the solutions (n=90)

Solution	Quantity
In-house development	1
GebMan	1
HIS	36
inova:finance	1
Country solution personnel	1
Make	14
PERSISKA	1
SAP	34
Untis	1

Frequency of solutions in country mentions (n=84).

Country	HIS	Make	SAP	SUM
Germany	36	14	32	82
Switzerland	0	0	1	1
Austria	0	0	1	1

Distribution of usage in relation to the number of students at the institution (n=84).

Size	HIS	Make	SAP	SUM
Up to 5.000	12	2	3	17
5,001 to 15,000	16	7	10	33
15,001 to 30,000	4	2	14	20
More than 30,000	4	3	7	14

Distribution of use in relation to type of facility (n=84).

Type	HIS	Make	SAP	SUM
University	14	7	23	44
University of Applied Sciences	20	6	10	36
Art / music high school	2	1	1	4

How many solutions are used in parallel (n=78)

Number of solutions in operation	Number of mentions
1	72
2	6

Which combinations of solutions are used (n=6)

The table is understood row by row with indications of 'Yes' within the same row if the respective solutions are used in parallel.

SAP	HIS	Make	Quantity
Yes	Yes	0	3
0	Yes	Yes	2
Yes	0	Yes	1

Overview of operating models and frequencies (n=75)

Solution	Operating model	Frequency
HIS	Operation outside the university by a service provider	3
HIS	Operation partly by us, partly by a service provider	1
HIS	Operation on own servers on site by us	29
Make	Operation outside the university by a service provider	2
Make	Operation partly by us, partly by a service provider	1
Make	Operation on own servers on site by us	10
SAP	Operation outside the university by a service provider	16
SAP	Operation outside the university by us	1
SAP	Operation on own servers on site by us	12

Which license types are used (n=101)

Solution	License model
In-house development	Self developed
HIS	Open source
Kanban Board	Open source
kanboard	Open source
ProjectLibre	Open source
Redmine	Open source
Wekan	Open source
GebMan	Commercial
HIS	Commercial
inova:finance	Commercial
Make	Commercial
Matrix42	Commercial
MS Planner	Commercial
ONLYOFFICE	Commercial
Planta	Commercial
SAP	Commercial
Service Now	Commercial
Stackfield	Commercial
Untis	Commercial
Visual Paradigm	Commercial
Zenkit Suite	Commercial
Country solution personnel	Hybrid
Plan.io (Commercial product based on Redmine)	Hybrid

Satisfaction with the solutions (n=64)

Solution	Min	Lower quartile	Average	Median	Upper quartile	Max	Number of entries
SAP	3.00	6.00	6.83	7.00	8.00	9.00	23.00
HIS	3.00	5.00	6.37	6.50	7.00	9.00	30.00
Make	3.00	5.00	6.00	7.00	7.00	8.00	11.00

Should the solution be replaced (n=3)

Solution	Intention to redeem
SAP	0
HIS	2
Make	1

By what should the solution be weaned

HIS	Make
CampusOnline	to specify
SAP	

Sync and Share

Summary of the results

Most frequent solutions in total (n=118)

Distribution by size of university (n=102)

Distribution by type of university sorted by solutions (n=102)

Distribution sorted by type of university (n=102)

Satisfaction with the solutions (n=86)

[Link for explanations of the boxplot](#)

Operating models of the solutions (n=96)

Individual tables of the evaluation

Frequencies of the solutions (n=128)

Solution	Quantity
Academic Cloud	1
Hessenbox	1
Micro Focus Filr	9
Microsoft OneDrive	9
MS Sharepoint	1
NetCase	1
NextCloud	59
OneDrive4Business	1
OwnCloud	14
PowerFolder	9
Sciebo (Owncloud)	7
Seafile	11
Strato HiDrive	1
SWITCHdrive	2
Sync & Share (LRZ)	1
TeamDrive via DFN	1

Frequency of solutions in country mentions (n=102).

Country	Micro Focus Filr	NextCloud	OwnCloud	PowerFolder	Seafile	SUM
Germany	8	56	13	9	11	97
Austria	0	3	1	0	0	4
Switzerland	1	0	0	0	0	1

Distribution of usage in relation to the number of students at the institution (n=102).

Size	Micro Focus Filr	NextCloud	OwnCloud	PowerFolder	Seafile	SUM
Up to 5.000	3	17	3	0	1	24
5,001 to 15,000	4	20	5	2	3	34
15,001 to 30,000	1	16	2	4	2	25
More than 30,000	1	6	4	3	5	19

Distribution of use in relation to type of facility (n=102).

Type	Micro Focus Filr	NextCloud	OwnCloud	PowerFolder	Seafile	SUM
University	3	35	8	7	7	60
University of Applied Sciences	6	20	5	2	3	36
Art / Music High School	0	3	1	0	0	4
Church university	0	0	0	0	1	1
State recognized private university	0	1	0	0	0	1

How many solutions are used in parallel (n=87)

Number of solutions in operation	Number of mentions
1	74
2	12
4	1

Which combinations of the solutions are used (n=13)

The table is understood line by line with indications of 'Yes' within the same line if the respective solutions are used in parallel.

NextCloud	OwnCloud	PowerFolder	Seafile	Micro Focus Filr	Quantity
Yes	0	0	0	Yes	3
0	Yes	0	Yes	0	2
Yes	0	0	Yes	0	2
Yes	0	Yes	0	0	2
Yes	Yes	0	0	0	2
0	Yes	0	0	Yes	1
Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	0	1

Overview of operating models and frequencies (n=96)

Solution	Operating model	Frequency
Micro Focus Filr	Operation on own servers on site by us	9
NextCloud	Operation outside the university by a service provider	13
NextCloud	Operation outside the university by us	1
NextCloud	Operation on own servers on site by us	40
OwnCloud	Operation outside the university by a service provider	7
OwnCloud	Operation on own servers on site by us	7
PowerFolder	Operation outside the university by a service provider	2
PowerFolder	Operation on own servers on site by a service provider	1
PowerFolder	Operation on own servers on site by us	5
Seafile	Operation outside the university by a service provider	2
Seafile	Operation on own servers on site by us	9

Which license types are used (n=120)

Solution	License model
Sync & Share (LRZ)	Self developed
Academic Cloud	Open source
NextCloud	Open source
OwnCloud	Open source
PowerFolder	Open source
Sciebo (Owncloud)	Open source
Seafile	Open source
SWITCHdrive	Open source
TeamDrive via DFN	Open source
Micro Focus Filr	Commercial
Microsoft OneDrive	Commercial
MS Sharepoint	Commercial
NextCloud	Commercial
OneDrive4Business	Commercial
OwnCloud	Commercial
PowerFolder	Commercial
Sciebo (Owncloud)	Commercial
Seafile	Commercial
Strato HiDrive	Commercial
NextCloud	Hybrid
OwnCloud	Hybrid
Sciebo (Owncloud)	Hybrid
Seafile	Hybrid
SWITCHdrive	Hybrid

Satisfaction with the solutions (n=86)

Solution	Min	Lower quartile	Average	Median	Upper quartile	Max	Number of entries
NextCloud	1.00	7.00	7.18	8.00	8.00	10.00	49.00
OwnCloud	1.00	6.00	6.43	7.00	7.00	8.00	14.00
PowerFolder	4.00	4.00	5.33	4.50	5.75	9.00	6.00
Seafile	2.00	7.00	7.33	8.00	9.00	10.00	9.00
Micro Focus Filr	2.00	4.00	6.12	7.00	8.00	9.00	8.00

Should the solution be replaced (n=7)

Solution	Intention to redeem
NextCloud	0
OwnCloud	2
PowerFolder	1
Seafile	1
Micro Focus Filr	3

By what should the solution be weaned

OwnCloud	PowerFolder	Seafile	Micro Focus Filr
NextCloud	NextCloud	Use of the Seafile instance of the ZDV of the JGU Mainz intended	NextCloud
Nextcloud			OwnCloud
			Microsoft OneDrive

Ticket / Incident Management

Summary of the results

Most frequent solutions in total (n=97)

Distribution according to size of the university (n=87)

Distribution by type of college sorted by solutions (n=87).

Distribution by type of college sorted by type (n=87).

Satisfaction with the solutions (n=73)

[Link for explanations of the boxplot](#)

Operating models of the solutions (n=80)

Individual tables of the evaluation

Frequencies of the solutions (n=118)

Solution	Quantity
Echolon	1
own solution	1
GLPI	1
helpline	1
i-net Helpdesk	1
Ivanti	1
JIRA	11
KIX Professional	15
Kyhelp	1
LTRS	2
Matrix42	3
OFORK	1
osTicket	4
Otobo	2
OTRS	38
Redmine	1
Request tracker	1
RT	1
RT (Request Tracker)	1
Service Now	1
SMAX	1
TOPdesk	6
Zammad	10
Znuny	13

Frequency of solutions in country mentions (n=87).

Country	JIRA	KIX Professional	OTRS	Zammad	Znuny	SUM
Germany	9	15	37	8	13	82
Austria	1	0	1	2	0	4
Switzerland	1	0	0	0	0	1

Distribution of usage in relation to the number of students at the institution (n=87).

Size	JIRA	KIX Professional	OTRS	Zammad	Znuny	SUM
Up to 5.000	2	3	3	7	1	16
5,001 to 15,000	6	6	14	3	1	30
15,001 to 30,000	2	4	13	0	6	25
More than 30,000	1	2	8	0	5	16

Distribution of use in relation to type of facility (n=87).

Type	JIRA	KIX Professional	OTRS	Zammad	Znuny	SUM
University	3	11	25	3	11	53
University of Applied Sciences	7	4	13	5	2	31
Church university	1	0	0	0	0	1
Art / Music High School	0	0	0	1	0	1
State recognized private university	0	0	0	1	0	1

How many solutions are used in parallel (n=84)

Number of solutions in operation	Number of mentions
1	81
2	3

Which combinations of the solutions are used (n=3)

The table is understood line by line with indications of 'Yes' within the same line if the respective solutions are used in parallel.

OTRS	KIX Professional	Zammad	Znuny	JIRA	Quantity
Yes	0	0	0	Yes	1
Yes	0	0	Yes	0	1
Yes	Yes	0	0	0	1

Overview of operating models and frequencies (n=80)

Solution	Operating model	Frequency
JIRA	Operation outside the university by a service provider	2
JIRA	Operation on own servers on site by us	8
KIX Professional	Operation on own servers on site by us	13
OTRS	Operation on own servers on site by us	35
Zammad	Operation on own servers on site by us	9
Znuny	Operation on own servers on site by us	13

Which license types are used (n=109)

Solution	License model
own solution	Self developed
GLPI	Open Source
JIRA	Open Source
KIX Professional	Open source
OFORK	Open source
osTicket	Open source
Otobo	Open source
OTRS	Open source
Redmine	Open source
Request tracker	Open source
RT	Open source
RT (Request Tracker)	Open source
Zammad	Open source
Znuny	Open source
Echolon	Commercial
helpline	Commercial
i-net Helpdesk	Commercial
Ivanti	Commercial
JIRA	Commercial
KIX Professional	Commercial
LTRS	Commercial
Matrix42	Commercial
OTRS	Commercial
Service Now	Commercial
SMAX	Commercial
TOPdesk	Commercial
KIX Professional	Hybrid
Otobo	Hybrid
OTRS	Hybrid
Znuny	Hybrid

Satisfaction with the solutions (n=73)

Solution	Min	Lower quartile	Average	Median	Upper quartile	Max	Number of entries
OTRS	1.00	5.00	6.07	7.00	7.00	9.00	29.00
KIX Professional	1.00	7.00	7.42	8.00	9.00	9.00	12.00
Zammad	6.00	8.00	8.67	9.00	10.00	10.00	9.00
Znuny	7.00	7.00	7.54	8.00	8.00	8.00	13.00
JIRA	7.00	8.00	8.20	8.00	9.00	9.00	10.00

Should the solution be replaced (n=11)

Solution	Intention to redeem
OTRS	9
KIX Professional	1
Zammad	0
Znuny	0
JIRA	1

By what should the solution be weaned

OTRS	KIX Professional	JIRA
Replaced by OFORK	Project to find replacement solution	Migration to cloud solution from JIRA if necessary
JIRA		
KIX		
still unknown.		
Zammad		
Replacement in planning possibly OTOBO		
Znuny or OTOBO		
Znuny		

Event Management

Summary of the results

Individual tables of the evaluation

Frequencies of the solutions:

Solution	Quantity
cobra EventManager	3
ConfTool	2
Converia	3
Campusnet Data Controllers	1
In-house development	1
GREEN eVEWA	1
HIS EXA VM	1
HIS LSF	2
Indico	5
SPF	1
Modern event calendar	1
Job ticket	1
StudIP	1
Ungerboeck	1
UnivIS	1
Zkipster	1

Type of licenses

Solution	License model
Indico	Open Source
StudIP	Hybrid
ConfTool	Commercial
Converia	Commercial
Campusnet Data Controllers	Commercial
GREEN eVEWA	Commercial
HIS EXA VM	Commercial
HIS LSF	Commercial
SPF	Commercial
Modern event calendar	Commercial
Job ticket	Commercial
Ungerboeck	Commercial
UnivIS	Commercial
Zkipster	Commercial
cobra EventManager	Commercial
In-house development	Self developed

Video conferencing

Summary of the results

Most frequent solutions in total (n=224)

Distribution according to size of university (n=212)

Distribution by type of college sorted by solutions (n=212).

Distribution sorted by type of university (n=212)

Satisfaction with the solutions (n=151)

Zufriedenheit mit der Lösung von 1 - sehr unzufrieden bis 10 - sehr zufrieden

[Link for explanations of the boxplot](#)

Operating models of the solutions (n=201)

Individual tables of the evaluation

Frequencies of the solutions (n=230)

Solution	Quantity
Adobe Connect	2
Alfaview	1
BigBlueButton	58
Cisco WebEx	32
ClickMeeting	1
DFNconf	4
Jitsi	8
Microsoft Teams	47
Skype for Business	1
Starleaf	1
Zoom	75

Frequency of solutions in country mentions (n=212).

Country	BigBlueButton	Cisco WebEx	Microsoft Teams	Zoom	SUM
Germany	57	28	41	68	194
Switzerland	0	2	5	5	12
Austria	1	2	1	2	6

Distribution of usage in relation to the number of students at the institution (n=212).

Size	BigBlueButton	Cisco WebEx	Microsoft Teams	Zoom	SUM
Up to 5.000	15	5	11	13	44
5,001 to 15,000	17	11	21	33	82
15,001 to 30,000	16	10	10	18	54
More than 30,000	10	6	5	11	32

Distribution of use in relation to type of facility (n=212).

Type	BigBlueButton	Cisco WebEx	Microsoft Teams	Zoom	SUM
University	37	20	18	41	116
University of Applied Sciences	20	9	26	29	84
State recognized private university	0	1	2	2	5
Church university	1	1	1	1	4
Art / Music High School	0	1	0	2	3

How many solutions are used in parallel (n=109)

Number of solutions in operation	Number of mentions
1	32
2	55
3	18
4	4

Which combinations of solutions are used (n=77)

The table is understood line by line with statements of 'Yes' within the same line if the respective solutions are used in parallel.

BigBlueButton	Zoom	Cisco WebEx	Microsoft Teams	Quantity
0	Yes	0	Yes	19
Yes	Yes	0	0	19
Yes	0	Yes	0	9
Yes	Yes	0	Yes	8
Yes	0	0	Yes	7
Yes	Yes	Yes	0	6
0	Yes	Yes	Yes	4
Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	4
0	0	Yes	Yes	1

Overview of operating models and frequencies (n=201)

Solution	Operating model	Frequency
BigBlueButton	Operation outside the university by a service provider	5
BigBlueButton	Operation outside the university by us	1
BigBlueButton	Operation partly by us, partly by a service provider	2
BigBlueButton	Operation on own servers on site by a service provider	2
BigBlueButton	Operation on own servers on site by us	45
Cisco WebEx	Operation outside the university by a service provider	24
Cisco WebEx	Operation outside the university by us	2
Cisco WebEx	Operation partly by us, partly by a service provider	2
Cisco WebEx	Operation on own servers on site by a service provider	1
Cisco WebEx	Operation on own servers on site by us	3
Microsoft Teams	Operation outside the university by a service provider	41
Microsoft Teams	Operation outside the university by us	1
Microsoft Teams	Operation partly by us, partly by a service provider	1
Microsoft Teams	Operation on own servers on site by us	2
Zoom	Operation outside the university by a service provider	60
Zoom	Operation outside the university by us	1
Zoom	Operation partly by us, partly by a service provider	5
Zoom	Operation on own servers on site by a service provider	2
Zoom	Operation on own servers on site by us	1

Which license types are used (n=220)

Solution	License model
BigBlueButton	Open source
Jitsi	Open source
Adobe Connect	Commercial
Alfaview	Commercial
BigBlueButton	Commercial
Cisco WebEx	Commercial
ClickMeeting	Commercial
DFNconf	Commercial
Microsoft Teams	Commercial
Skype for Business	Commercial
Starleaf	Commercial
Zoom	Commercial
Zoom	Hybrid

Satisfaction with the solutions (n=151)

Solution	Min	Lower quartile	Average	Median	Upper quartile	Max	Number of entries
BigBlueButton	1.00	8.00	8.18	9.00	9.00	10.00	68.00
Zoom	2.00	7.00	7.75	8.00	9.00	10.00	28.00
Cisco WebEx	1.00	8.00	8.09	8.00	9.00	10.00	43.00
Microsoft Teams	4.00	6.00	6.67	7.00	7.00	10.00	12.00

Should the solution be replaced (n=10)

Solution	Intention to redeem
BigBlueButton	1
Zoom	3
Cisco WebEx	6
Microsoft Teams	0

By what should the solution be weaned

BigBlueButton	Zoom	Cisco WebEx
Zoom or MS Teams	It is still open whether we will do without Zoom or only switch to the telecom variant	is replaced
	MS Teams	Zoom
	Cisco WebEx	Further use unclear due to data protection issues
		Will be replaced if necessary, as the contract expires in October 2022
		no further use planned in the future
		zoom, MS Teams

Video Management

Summary of the results

Most frequent solutions in total (n=72)

Distribution according to size of university (n=68)

Distribution by type of college sorted by solutions (n=68).

Distribution sorted by type of university (n=68)

Satisfaction with the solutions (n=48)

[Link for explanations of the boxplot](#)

Operating models of the solutions (n=62)

Individual tables of the evaluation

Frequencies of the solutions (n=87)

Solution	Quantity
Camtasia	2
eLectures	1
Flowcasts	1
Kaltura	1
Lecture2Go	1
Media Library	1
MediaSite	4
MS Stream	2
OpenCast	35
Panopto	17
Planet eStream	1
Presentations2Go	1
SWITCHcast	1
VBrick	1
Vimeo	2
Vimp	16

Frequency of solutions in country mentions (n=68).

Country	OpenCast	Panopto	Vimp	SUM
Germany	33	16	16	65
Switzerland	1	1	0	2
Austria	1	0	0	1

Distribution of usage in relation to the number of students at the institution (n=68).

Size	OpenCast	Panopto	Vimp	SUM
Up to 5,000	5	1	6	12
5,001 to 15,000	13	11	7	31
15,001 to 30,000	11	4	2	17
More than 30,000	6	1	1	8

Distribution of use in relation to type of facility (n=68).

Type	OpenCast	Panopto	Vimp	SUM
University	22	9	7	38
University of Applied Sciences	13	8	9	30

How many solutions are used in parallel (n=66)

Number of solutions in operation	Number of mentions
1	64
2	2

Which combinations of the solutions are used (n=2)

The table is understood line by line with indications of 'Yes' within the same line if the respective solutions are used in parallel.

OpenCast	Panopto	Vimp	Quantity
0	Yes	Yes	1
Yes	0	Yes	1

Overview of operating models and frequencies (n=62)

Solution	Operating model	Frequency
OpenCast	Operation outside the university by a service provider	2
OpenCast	Operation partly by us, partly by a service provider	2
OpenCast	Operation on own servers on site by a service provider	4
OpenCast	Operation on own servers on site by us	25
Panopto	Operation outside the university by a service provider	8
Panopto	Operation outside the university by us	2
Panopto	Operation on own servers on site by us	4
Vimp	Operation outside the university by a service provider	1
Vimp	Operation outside the university by us	1
Vimp	Operation partly by us, partly by a service provider	1
Vimp	Operation on own servers on site by us	12

Which license types are used (n=98)

Solution	License model
Flowcasts	Self developed
OpenCast	Self developed
SWITCHcast	Self developed
Jitsi	Open source
Lecture2Go	Open source
OpenCast	Open source
Vimp	Open source
Adobe Connect	Commercial
Alfaview	Commercial
Camtasia	Commercial
ClickMeeting	Commercial
DFNconf	Commercial
Kaltura	Commercial
Media Library	Commercial
MediaSite	Commercial
MS Stream	Commercial
Panopto	Commercial
Planet eStream	Commercial
Presentations2Go	Commercial
Skype for Business	Commercial
Starleaf	Commercial
VBrick	Commercial
Vimeo	Commercial
Vimp	Commercial

Satisfaction with the solutions (n=48)

Solution	Min	Lower quartile	Average	Median	Upper quartile	Max	Number of entries
OpenCast	5.00	7.00	7.48	7.00	8.00	9.00	23.00
Panopto	2.00	8.00	8.00	8.00	9.00	10.00	13.00
Vimp	6.00	6.75	7.50	7.50	8.25	9.00	12.00

Should the solution be replaced (n=2)

Solution	Intention to redeem
OpenCast	1
Panopto	0
Vimp	1

By what should the solution be weaned

OpenCast	Vimp
Panopto	OpenCast

Virtualization / IaaS

Summary of the results

Most frequent solutions in total (n=132)

Distribution by size of university (n=132)

Distribution by type of university sorted by solutions (n=132)

Distribution sorted by type of university (n=132)

Satisfaction with the solutions (n=104)

[Link for explanations of the boxplot](#)

Operating models of the solutions (n=126)

Individual tables of the evaluation

Frequencies of the solutions (n=142)

Solution	Quantity
Microsoft Hyper-V	19
Nutanix	1
OpenStack	3
Oracle VM	1
oVirt	1
Proxmox	16
RHEV	1
SWITCHengines	1
VMWare	97
XEN-ng	1
XenServer NG	1

Frequency of solutions in country mentions (n=132).

Country	Microsoft Hyper-V	Proxmox	VMWare	SUM
Germany	18	16	89	123
Switzerland	1	0	5	6
Austria	0	0	3	3

Distribution of usage in relation to the number of students at the institution (n=132).

Size	Microsoft Hyper-V	Proxmox	VMWare	SUM
Up to 5.000	4	2	22	28
5,001 to 15,000	4	5	37	46
15,001 to 30,000	7	6	24	37
More than 30,000	4	3	14	21

Distribution of use in relation to type of facility (n=132).

Type	Microsoft Hyper-V	Proxmox	VMWare	SUM
University	12	12	54	78
University of Applied Sciences	5	4	39	48
Art / Music High School	0	0	3	3
State recognized private university	2	0	0	2
Church university	0	0	1	1

How many solutions are used in parallel (n=103)

Number of solutions in operation	Number of mentions
1	79
2	19
3	5

Which combinations of solutions are used (n=24)

The table is understood row by row with statements of 'Yes' within the same row if the respective solutions are used in parallel.

VMWare	Proxmox	Microsoft Hyper-V	Quantity
Yes	0	Yes	10
Yes	Yes	0	9
Yes	Yes	Yes	5

Overview of operating models and frequencies (n=126)

Solution	Operating model	Frequency
Microsoft Hyper-V	Operation on own servers on site by us	19
Proxmox	Operation on own servers on site by us	15
VMWare	Operation outside the university by us	1
VMWare	Operation on own servers on site by us	91

Which license types are used (n=146)

Solution	License model
Jitsi	Open source
OpenStack	Open source
oVirt	Open Source
Proxmox	Open Source
SWITCHengines	Open source
VMWare	Open source
XEN-ng	Open source
XenServer NG	Open source
Adobe Connect	Commercial
Alfaviw	Commercial
ClickMeeting	Commercial
DFNconf	Commercial
Microsoft Hyper-V	Commercial
Oracle VM	Commercial
Proxmox	Commercial
RHEV	Commercial
Skype for Business	Commercial
Starleaf	Commercial
VMWare	Commercial
Proxmox	Hybrid
VMWare	Hybrid

Satisfaction with the solutions (n=104)

Solution	Min	Lower quartile	Average	Median	Upper quartile	Max	Number of entries
VMWare	1.00	8.00	8.16	9.00	9.00	10.00	82.00
Proxmox	1.00	7.00	7.40	7.50	9.00	10.00	10.00
Microsoft Hyper-V	1.00	6.50	7.17	8.00	9.00	10.00	12.00

Should the solution be replaced (n=3)

Solution	Intention to redeem
VMWare	0
Proxmox	0
Microsoft Hyper-V	3

By what should the solution be weaned

Microsoft Hyper-V
Nutanix
Hyper-V
VMware

Knowledge Management

Summary of the results

Most frequent solutions in total (n=106)

Distribution according to size of university (n=106)

Distribution by type of college sorted by solutions (n=106).

Distribution sorted by type of university (n=106)

Satisfaction with the solutions (n=60)

[Link for explanations of the boxplot](#)

Operating models of the solutions (n=104)

Individual tables of the evaluation

Frequencies of the solutions (n=113)

Solution	Quantity
Confluence	41
dokuwiki	16
Foswiki	1
lexican	1
Mediawiki	23
Microsoft SharePoint	26
Plone	1
SharePointOnline	1
Trac	1
Twiki	1
XWiki	1

Frequency of solutions in country mentions (n=106).

Country	Confluence	Mediawiki	Microsoft SharePoint	dokuwiki	SUM
Germany	35	22	23	14	94
Switzerland	4	0	2	1	7
Austria	2	1	1	1	5

Distribution of usage in relation to the number of students at the institution (n=106).

Size	Confluence	Mediawiki	Microsoft SharePoint	dokuwiki	SUM
Up to 5.000	5	4	6	2	17
5,001 to 15,000	18	7	9	8	42
15,001 to 30,000	11	7	6	4	28
More than 30,000	7	5	5	2	19

Distribution of use in relation to type of facility (n=106).

Type	Confluence	Mediawiki	Microsoft SharePoint	dokuwiki	SUM
University	21	15	14	10	60
University of Applied Sciences	19	8	10	6	43
State recognized private university	0	0	2	0	2
Church university	1	0	0	0	1

How many solutions are used in parallel (n=79)

Number of solutions in operation	Number of mentions
1	59
2	15
3	3
4	2

Which combinations of the solutions are used (n=20)

The table is understood line by line with indications of 'Yes' within the same line if the respective solutions are used in parallel.

Confluence	Microsoft SharePoint	Mediawiki	dokuwiki	Quantity
Yes	Yes	0	0	6
0	0	Yes	Yes	3
Yes	0	0	Yes	3
Yes	0	Yes	0	2
Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	2
0	Yes	Yes	0	1
0	Yes	Yes	Yes	1
Yes	Yes	0	Yes	1
Yes	Yes	Yes	0	1

Overview of operating models and frequencies (n=104)

Solution	Operating model	Frequency
Confluence	Operation outside the university by a service provider	3
Confluence	Operation outside the university by us	2
Confluence	Operation on own servers on site by us	35
Mediawiki	Operation on own servers on site by us	22
Microsoft SharePoint	Operation outside the university by a service provider	9
Microsoft SharePoint	Operation partly by us, partly by a service provider	1
Microsoft SharePoint	Operation on own servers on site by us	16
dokuwiki	Operation on own servers on site by us	16

Which license types are used (n=108)

Solution	License model
Confluence	Open Source
dokuwiki	Open Source
Foswiki	Open source
Mediawiki	Open source
Plone	Open source
Trac	Open source
Twiki	Open source
XWiki	Open source
Confluence	Commercial
lexican	Commercial
Microsoft SharePoint	Commercial
SharePointOnline	Commercial

Satisfaction with the solutions (n=60)

Solution	Min	Lower quartile	Average	Median	Upper quartile	Max	Number of entries
Confluence	3.00	6.00	6.79	7.00	8.00	10.00	24.00
Microsoft SharePoint	6.00	6.00	7.28	7.00	8.00	10.00	18.00
Mediawiki	4.00	6.75	7.42	8.00	8.00	9.00	12.00
dokuwiki	6.00	7.25	7.50	8.00	8.00	8.00	6.00

Should the solution be replaced (n=9)

Solution	Intention to redeem
Confluence	3
Microsoft SharePoint	2
Mediawiki	2
dokuwiki	2

By what should the solution be weaned

Confluence	Microsoft SharePoint	Mediawiki	dokuwiki
Migration to cloud solution of Confluence if necessary	Microsoft Sharepoint Online	MS Sharepoint, DocBook	Confluene
to decide	SharePoint online	Confluence and XWiki	MS Sharepoint, DocBook
			Confluence

List of questions

General questions: Please provide us with some basic information.

- From which type of university or research institution do you come? (University, University of Applied Sciences, University of Art / Music, Church university, Dual university, State-recognized private university, Research institution)
- In which country is your facility located?
- In which state is your facility located? (List of federal states)
- How many students does your university have? (Up to 5,000, 5,001 to 15,000, 15,001 to 30,000, More than 30,000)

Questions for each software category:

- Which solution do you use? (Specifications from the top answers of the 2021 survey or as an additional free-text answer)
- Is the system commercial, open source, self-developed or hybrid³? (Commercial, Open Source, Self-developed, Hybrid)
- How do you operate the system? Internally, externally or mixed? (Operation on own servers on site by us, operation on own servers on site by a service provider, operation outside the university by us, operation outside the university by a service provider, operation partly by us, partly by a service provider).
- How do you rate the satisfaction of the users?
- Is one of the above systems to be replaced or is in the process of being replaced?
 - (Name the system you plan to use instead).

³ <https://de.wikipedia.org/wiki/Mehrfachlizenzierung>